

**INVESTIGATING THE CONTINUING PROFESSIONAL DEVELOPMENT
PROGRAMS AND PRACTICES OF COLLEGE ENGLISH LANGUAGE
TEACHERS IN SELECTED SUCS IN MIMAROPA
REGION, PHILIPPINES**

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Investigating the Continuing Professional Development Programs and Practices of College English Language Teachers in Selected SUCS in MIMAROPA Region, Philippines

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Abstract

This study attempted to explore the Continuing Professional Development (CPD) programs and practices of college English language teachers in the MIMAROPA region of the Philippines. Specifically, it focused on determining the engagement levels in professional formal and personal activities of CPD and teacher practices, finding the teachers' attitudes, views, and perceptions towards CPD, finding out CPD influence, impact on content and pedagogy of teachers, and CPD challenges. The research used mixed method with multiphase design through survey questionnaires (78 respondents) and interviews (5) participants. Quantitative data were treated with Mean and Pearson r while qualitative data were narratively analyzed. The findings highlight very high engagement in both formal and personal CPD activities, with highly practiced outcomes in training, awards bearing, coaching, and mentoring, community of practice, action research, and transformative model. Additionally, teachers generally strongly agree in having positive attitudes, views, and perceptions towards CPD, recognizing its value in enhancing teaching skills and effectiveness. Notably, there was a strong positive correlation between the extent of CPD engagement and its practices, and a moderately positive correlation between CPD engagement and teachers' attitudes, views, and perceptions. The impact of CPD on improving pedagogical approaches, content knowledge, and overall teaching performance is significant, with teachers noting improvements in their ELT practices. Challenges encountered include balancing work-based activities, personal engagement, institutional barriers, and fostering community practices, which teachers aim to overcome through further research, collaboration, and reflective practices.

Keywords: *continuing professional development (cpd), english language teaching (elt), community of practice, transformative model*

Introduction

Teachers' Continuing Professional Development (CPD) is crucial for enhancing professional skills and teaching effectiveness. While globally recognized, CPD includes both formal and personal practices, leading to theoretical and empirical debates. Faculty development activities can improve teaching skills, subject knowledge, and classroom management.

Studies highlight the importance of CPD in achieving student satisfaction and improving teacher performance (Nairz-Wirth & Feldmann, 2019; Subitha, 2019). In the Philippines, the CPD Act of 2016 mandates teachers to acquire CPD units for license renewal, aiming to align with international norms (Paliwal, 2016). Effective CPD programs equip teachers with current knowledge, teaching techniques, and professional ethics (Glatthorn et al., 2018).

In a rapidly evolving educational landscape, teachers must continuously adapt to new demands to foster student success (Paniagua & Istance, 2018). This study evaluates CPD practices for English Language teachers in the MIMAROPA region, addressing gaps in existing literature and contributing to the development of effective, tailored CPD models.

This research underscores the importance of CPD in improving teaching quality, promoting lifelong learning, and meeting regulatory requirements. Enhanced CPD ultimately leads to better educational experiences for students by equipping teachers with the necessary skills and knowledge.

Research Questions

This research sought to investigate the continuing professional development programs and the practices of college English language teachers in the MIMAROPA Region, Philippines. Specifically, this study sought answers to the following questions;

1. What continuing professional development programs that college English language teachers in MIMAROPA region are engaged in terms of professional work-based activities and personal activities?
2. What are the continuing professional development practices of college English language teachers in MIMAROPA region in terms of training, award bearing, coaching or mentoring, the community of practice, the action research, and the transformative model?
3. What attitudes, views, and perceptions are held by college English language teachers in the MIMAROPA region about continuing professional development programs?
4. Is there a significant relationship between the extent of engagement on CPD and CPD practices of college English language teachers in the MIMAROPA region?
5. Is there a significant relationship between the extent of engagement on CPD and attitudes, views, and perceptions of college English language teachers in the MIMAROPA region about CPD programs?

6. To what extent do the CPD programs and practices of college English language teachers in the MIMAROPA region influence their performance in ELT and their behavior towards English?
7. What are the impacts of these continuing development programs to the pedagogical and content knowledge of college English language teachers in the MIMAROPA region?
8. How do the CPD programs and practices of college English language teachers in MIMAROPA region improve their pedagogy?
9. What are the challenges faced by the college English language teachers in the MIMAROPA region as regards their continuing professional development program?

Literature Review

Continuing Professional Development (CPD) Activities

An effective teacher's continuing professional development (CPD) is comprehensive, lifelong, and influenced by various factors, including teachers' beliefs, contexts, and personal circumstances (Hayes et al., 2019). CPD can be initiated by teachers or mandated by third parties, with the implementation at the school level influenced by working environments and teachers' attitudes toward their jobs. Peleman et al. (2018) found that long-term CPD interventions, such as coaching and pedagogical guidance, are effective in improving educational methods across different contexts. Faulkner et al. (2019) highlighted the success of international models of CPD for out-of-field teachers, showing the importance of context-specific approaches. Mukn et al. (2019) emphasized that CPD helps in establishing values, skills, and knowledge, bridging educational changes and continuous professional development. Bendtsen et al. (2022) highlighted the importance of collaboration and integration of CPD courses into practice for sustainable professional growth. GV (2018) critiqued the current paradigm of teacher professional development, advocating for teacher autonomy and sociocultural context-based learning. Masoumi et al. (2019) mapped faculty professional development in Iran, highlighting the challenges and potential improvements in higher education. O'Toole (2019) discussed the benefits of networked learning communities for CPD, emphasizing the need for collaboration among faculty members. Nooruddin and Bhamani (2019) demonstrated the structural approach to CPD in schools, focusing on personalized teacher development plans. Ozer et al. (2020) stressed the importance of individualized professional development plans for teachers. Richards (2019) identified three models of professional development: top-down, bottom-up, and interactive, with the interactive model being the most effective. Rimmer and Floyd (2020) supported the interactive model, emphasizing formal and informal learning within professional communities. Berbain et al. (2023) suggested that effective CPD includes developing pedagogical skills, reflective teaching, and interpersonal traits. Allen et al. (2019) categorized CPD activities into expertise, self-reflection, and cooperation with colleagues. Vadivel et al. (2021) highlighted the importance of collaborative CPD methods in enhancing teaching practices. Yucedag and Sevik (2021) found that collaborative CPD activities lead to optimal learning outcomes. Allison (2023) linked CPD involvement to improvements in teaching strategies, decision-making, and instructional modifications. Hayes (2019) showed that English language teachers benefit from regular seminars and collaborative curriculum development. Sepulveda-Escobar (2020) emphasized the effectiveness of collaborative syllabus development in enhancing teaching practices. Derakhshan et al. (2020) found that action research projects help English language teachers improve their instructional practices. Sifakis et al. (2022) suggested that collaborating with industry professionals enhances real-world language applications. Phiri (2020) highlighted the benefits of attending research conferences for staying updated on advancements in English language education. Abakah (2023) showed that mentorship programs and publishing articles enhance teachers' professional development. Personal learning activities, such as self-directed reading, watching educational videos, and engaging in professional networks, further contribute to teachers' CPD (Olivier & Wittmann, 2019; Helate et al., 2022; Al Ofi, 2022; Njenga, 2023). Reflective practices and cultural immersion experiences are also important for enhancing teaching effectiveness (Al-Ismael et al., 2023; Cirocki & Farrell, 2019). Participating in book clubs and professional associations, as well as engaging in ancillary services, are valuable for professional growth (Qadhi & Floyd, 2021; Had & Ab Rashid, 2019; Leeder et al., 2021). Dhanavel (2022) emphasized the active role of teachers in program planning and development to improve language teaching practices.

Continuing Professional Development Practices

In addition to professional work-related and personal activities in continuing professional development (CPD), this study aimed to investigate the CPD practices of English teachers, as highlighted by Abakah et al. (2022), who identified nine CPD models within Kennedy's CPD framework, including coaching/mentoring, community of practice, action research, standard-based, deficit, cascade, award-bearing, training, and transformative models. These models, categorized into transmissive, transitional, and transformative, enable teachers to adapt to educational changes while promoting ownership of their learning. Transformative models, such as action research and collaborative professional inquiry, foster reflective practice and critical evaluation of teaching methods, ultimately influencing educational goals. Maqbali et al. (2022) examined CPD for PE teachers in Oman, revealing the importance of ongoing development for CPD providers, while Tulu (2019) found that secondary school teachers in Hawassa City Administration valued CPD despite challenges. Molway (2019) emphasized the role of specialized training workshops, while Utami et al. (2019) highlighted the significance of online certification courses for technology-assisted language instruction. Cross-disciplinary training and seminars by renowned educators were identified as beneficial practices by Bayram and Canaran (2020) and Mann and Webb (2022). Purnamasari (2019) found that in-house training sessions tailored to specific challenges were effective, and Shen and Bai (2019) emphasized the importance of advanced language courses for personal proficiency. Borg et al. (2020) highlighted the value of peer-assisted professional

development, while Farrell (2020) emphasized community-specific training programs.

Wong (2023) and Price (2020) discussed the pursuit of external certifications for professional recognition, and MacKay et al. (2022) highlighted context-specific certifications. Bentall and Hunt (2022) explored the role of third-sector organizations in CPD, while Sey (2023) emphasized the importance of relevant CPD in Cambodian high schools. Shankar (2022) highlighted proactive engagement in CPD at the tertiary level, and Orsdemir and Yildirim (2020) emphasized the value of mentoring in ELT practicum settings. Communities of practice, as explored by Orsini-Jones et al. (2022), Keuk (2022), Slogoski (2019), and Mehdizadeh et al. (2023), play a critical role in professional growth. Online communities, such as those studied by Mai et al. (2020), provide valuable resources for continuous learning. Sato and Loewen (2019) and Bakhshi et al. (2019) emphasized the importance of action research in informing teaching practices, while Rahimi et al. (2019) and Yüce (2019) highlighted the role of research in professional identity construction. Dawadi (2021) and Mazandarani (2022) emphasized the value of thematic analysis and adapting action research to current teaching trends. Sifakis and Kordia (2019), Barjesteh (2019), Quintero-Polo et al. (2022), Nitta and Yamamoto (2020), Paschal and Gougou (2022), and Song (2019) highlighted the transformative model's impact on teaching practices, emphasizing the importance of critical reflection and social and cultural dimensions in language teaching.

Attitudes, Views, and Perception about CPD programs

According to Suliman et al. (2020), continuing professional development (CPD) is crucial for public benefit, individual growth, and professional enhancement, maintaining knowledge and skills, improving credibility, and ensuring professionals stay current with industry advancements. However, professionals face obstacles like time constraints and workload that hinder CPD participation. Saade et al. (2018) found similar barriers among pharmacists in Lebanon, including lack of time, job constraints, and accessibility to group learning events, with significant correlations between motivation, barriers, and attitudes towards CPD. Allen (2019) and Allen et al. (2021) highlighted the need for broader CPD impact assessments, developing a comprehensive CPD Impacts Survey (CPDIS) to evaluate a wide range of CPD effects, indicating the necessity for professional development in keeping knowledge current. Grehan et al. (2023) discussed the decline in CPD emphasis among radiographers in Ireland, with time becoming a primary obstacle over funding. Abakah et al. (2023) noted that Ghanaian teachers utilized distance education (DE) for CPD despite structural and content issues, suggesting regularizing alternative CPD routes and updating DE programs. Teslo et al. (2023) emphasized the benefits of CPD programs for diversifying teaching methods and promoting reflection. Borg (2016) and Goa (2021) stressed viewing CPD as a continuous, integrated process, enhancing teachers' engagement and efficacy. Lo and To (2023) found that CPD increased teachers' curiosity and desire for school-integrated CPD during the COVID-19 pandemic. Alamari (2019) and Koirala (2023) highlighted teachers' interest in CPD and its role in developing 21st-century skills, critical thinking, and career advancement. Onalan and Gursoy (2020) emphasized the need for relevant in-service training for EFL teachers in Turkey. Tsagari et al. (2023) and Wulyani et al. (2021) underscored CPD's impact on language assessment and teacher research, respectively, advocating for ongoing support and resources. Mekie and Gezahegn (2023) and Eryilmaz (2021) found that CPD programs enhance cognitive and organizational skills. Xerri (2023) highlighted CPD's positive impact on TESOL practitioners in Malta, while Goa (2021) and Lo and To (2023) emphasized the benefits of needs-based CPD and action research for addressing challenges and improving teaching practices. Koirala (2023) and Al-Wadi (2023) noted the motivational impact of award-bearing CPD programs and their role in pedagogical improvement. Overall, these studies underline the importance of tailored, ongoing CPD programs that address specific professional needs, promote reflective practice, and support continuous learning and adaptation in teaching.

Influence of CPD on Performance in ELT and Pedagogy

Karamatdinova's research (2023) in Uzbekistan highlights the significant impact of Continuous Professional Development (CPD) on inexperienced educators, providing them with essential skills and knowledge, boosting their confidence, and enhancing classroom performance and student outcomes. Al Balushi (2021) found similar benefits for TESOL teachers in Oman, where CPD programs improved pedagogical skills and language competency, fostering a culture of ongoing learning and increasing teacher retention. Mekonnen (2019) identified challenges in Ethiopia, such as limited resources and institutional support, but emphasized the need for investment in CPD to enhance professional competence. Wardani et al. (2023) in Indonesia stressed the importance of tailored CPD programs for Islamic junior high school English teachers, suggesting workshops, seminars, peer observation, and mentoring. Siregar and Mirizon (2021) also underscored the necessity of CPD for senior high school English teachers to stay updated with pedagogical practices, recommending ongoing, practical, and collaborative CPD initiatives. Marzaini et al. (2023) discussed the role of CPD in implementing CEFR-aligned assessments, emphasizing the need for assessment literacy. Spangenberg and Freitas (2019) identified obstacles to ICT integration in math teaching, while Somantri and Iskandar (2021) emphasized the comprehensive nature of CPD beyond teacher preparation. Barr (2019) highlighted the benefits of the Leadership for Inclusion in the Early Years (LINC) program in promoting inclusive and child-centered practices. Lee et al. (2018) and Gess-Newsome et al. (2019) demonstrated the importance of subject matter knowledge and pedagogical content knowledge (PCK) in teacher development.

Kang et al. (2018) found that professional development programs could enhance teachers' confidence in implementing science and engineering practices. Noormohammadi and Bhamani (2019) stressed the impact of CPD on student success. Nessaei and Kazemi (2024) and Dewi et al. (2020) highlighted the positive correlation between CPD participation and Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge (TPCK) and pedagogical content knowledge (PCK), respectively. Saricoban and Kirmizi (2020) emphasized the holistic

impact of CPD on pedagogical knowledge. Viana and Lu (2021) and Rachmajanti et al. (2019) underscored the integration of modern tools and reflective practices in CPD. Fitzpatrick et al. (2022) highlighted continuous reflection in professional development. Diklitas and Comoglu (2022) and Avillanova and Kuswandono (2019) advocated for socially mediated CPD activities, emphasizing collaborative knowledge reconstruction. Wyatt and Darwish (2022) contrasted top-down and bottom-up PD programs. Indrarathne and Dick (2023) and Sadeghi and Richards (2021) identified financial and time constraints as significant barriers to CPD. Mohammed and Gutema (2023) and Kedir and Gutema (2021) highlighted the lack of institutional support and access to quality CPD programs. Mekie and Gezahegn (2022) and Mwinuka and Farrelly (2023) emphasized the need for tailored CPD programs and increased institutional support. Cruz (2022) and Fernandez et al. (2022) identified resistance to change and time constraints as challenges in CPD engagement, underscoring the need for adaptable and supportive CPD programs to enhance professional development in language education.

Methodology

This study utilized Creswell's (2007) mixed-method approach, specifically the multiphase mixed-methods design, to investigate the professional development needs of college English language teachers. The quantitative component involved statistical techniques to analyze data from various levels, while the qualitative component comprised interviews to provide a comprehensive understanding of the phenomenon. The study examined teachers' participation in CPD programs, including professional and personal activities, CPD practices, and attitudes toward CPD in the MIMAROPA region. Quantitative data provided a foundation, with subsequent qualitative data offering deeper insights into teachers' experiences. Survey questionnaires and interviews, based on guidelines from the Department of Budget and Management (DBM) and the Commission on Higher Education (CHED), were used as the main data collection tools. The researcher-developed questionnaire, validated by experts, covered engagement in CPD programs, CPD practices, and teachers' attitudes. The interview guide assessed the impacts of CPD on pedagogical and content knowledge, challenges faced, and improvements in pedagogy.

Data collection followed a methodical approach, with surveys distributed, completed, and retrieved under strict guidelines, and interviews conducted and transcribed for further analysis. The validity and reliability of the instruments were ensured through expert reviews and pilot testing, achieving high Cronbach's alpha scores. The study involved 78 survey respondents and 5 interview participants, selected through random and purposive sampling, respectively. Data analysis employed descriptive statistics, Pearson's *r*, and narrative analysis to derive themes. Ethical considerations included informed consent and data confidentiality, adhering to the Data Privacy Act. The research was conducted in selected SUCs in the MIMAROPA region, chosen for their diverse geographical representation and substantial student populations. The study aimed to test hypotheses on the relationships between CPD engagement, practices, and attitudes, providing a comprehensive understanding of CPD's impact and leading to the development of a proposed CPD Program for English Language Teachers.

Results and Discussion

This part presents the results and analysis of the survey and interviews to the ELT teachers in the focused on the college English language teachers within MIMAROPA and their experienced with CPD. It covers investigation on the various aspects of CPD, including the engagement of teachers in professional work-based activities and personal activities, the CPD practices encompassing training, award-bearing, coaching or mentoring, the community of practice, conducting action research, and use of transformative models, as well as the attitudes, views, and perceptions held by these teachers regarding CPD programs. Furthermore, this part also presents interviews conducted on the influence of CPD programs on teaching performance and behavior towards English, the impacts of CPD programs and improvement on pedagogical and content knowledge, and the challenges encountered in CPD.

Table 1. Summary Data on College Language Teachers Level of Engagement in Continuing Professional Development (CPD) in terms of Professional Work-Based Activities and Personal activities

Work-Based Activities	Min	Max	Mean	VI
Formal	1	4	3.27	Very High Engagement
Personal	1	4	3.29	Very High Engagement
General Mean			3.28	Very High Engagement

Note. *N* = 78; Min = minimum; Max = maximum; VI = verbal interpretation.

Adopted from: Lacs, M. E. B. (2022). Learning activity sheets (LAS) and the English achievement of grade 8 students. *International Multidisciplinary Research Journal*, 4(1), 38-44. E-ISSN: 2378-702X

Legend: 1.00 – 1.75 Very Low Engagement; 1.76 – 2.50 Low Engagement; 2.51 – 3.25 High Engagement; 3.26 – 4.00 Very High Engagement

The data from Table 1 show that college English language teachers exhibit a high level of engagement in continuing professional development (CPD) activities, with formal and personal CPD activities having Means of 3.27 and 3.29 respectively, resulting in an overall Mean of 3.28, indicating very high engagement. This reflects a strong commitment to both structured and self-directed professional growth, emphasizing the value teachers place on a wide range of CPD opportunities, from seminars and workshops to self-study and peer learning. Such engagement is crucial in the evolving field of language education, as it helps teachers stay updated with the latest pedagogical research, methodologies, and technological tools. The balanced involvement in both formal and personal CPD activities shows that teachers are motivated by a genuine interest in lifelong learning and self-improvement, ultimately benefiting their students through more effective teaching practices. This high level of engagement aligns with findings from Bendtsen (2022), GV

(2018), and Ozer et al. (2020), which highlight the importance of diverse and individualized CPD activities in fostering continuous learning and professional development among teachers.

Table 2. *Summary Data on Continuing Professional Development Practices of College English Language Teachers in MIMAROPA Region in Terms of Training, Award Bearing, Coaching or Mentoring, the Community of Practice, the Action Research, and the Transformative Model*

CPD Practices	Min	Max	Mean	VI
Training	1	4	3.16	Highly Practiced
Awards Bearing	1	4	3.10	Highly Practiced
Coaching and Mentoring	1	4	3.20	Highly Practiced
Community of Practice	1	4	3.16	Highly Practiced
Action Research	1	4	3.10	Highly Practiced
Transformative Model	1	4	3.22	Highly Practiced
General Mean			3.16	Highly Practiced

Note. $N = 78$; Min = minimum; Max = maximum; VI = verbal interpretation.

Adopted from: Lacs, M. E. B. (2022). Learning activity sheets (LAS) and the English achievement of grade 8 students. *International Multidisciplinary Research Journal*, 4(1), 38-44. E-ISSN: 2378-702X

Legend: 1.00 – 1.75 Very Low Engagement; 1.76 – 2.50 Low Engagement; 2.51 – 3.25 High Engagement; 3.26 – 4.00 Very High Engagement

Table 2 summarizes the continuing professional development (CPD) practices of college English language teachers in the MIMAROPA region, highlighting training, awards bearing, coaching and mentoring, community of practice, action research, and the transformative model. Leading the CPD practices is the transformative model, with a Mean of 3.22, reflecting teachers' commitment to innovative professional growth. Training and coaching/mentoring follow closely with Means of 3.20, underscoring their role in skill enhancement and fostering collaborative learning. Both training and community of practice, each with a Mean of 3.16, emphasize the significance of collaboration and knowledge sharing among educators. Action research and awards bearing, both with a Mean of 3.10, highlight teachers' dedication to research-driven improvements and professional recognition. The overall general Mean for all practices is 3.16, indicating a high level of engagement in CPD practices and reflecting positive attitudes toward professional development. This data reveals a strong commitment to various CPD practices among educators, showcasing their recognition of the importance of ongoing growth across multiple dimensions. The high engagement in coaching and mentoring, and the transformative model, points to a forward-looking approach that prioritizes innovation, personalized learning, and the active application of new methodologies. For college English language teachers, a broad and committed approach to CPD is essential for maintaining high teaching standards and adapting to the evolving demands of language education. This diversity in CPD practices enriches teachers' professional experiences and enhances their ability to provide quality education, reflecting their capacity to innovate, engage, and inspire students. Institutions supporting English language educators should continue to foster an environment that values and facilitates diverse CPD activities, recognizing their role in sustaining educational excellence and teacher satisfaction. The significant engagement in CPD practices observed by Magbali et al. (2022) and Tulu (2019) underscores a prevailing commitment within the profession towards ongoing growth. Magbali et al. (2022) identified a pervasive aspiration among teachers to continually refine their skills, driven by personal fulfillment and career progression. Tulu (2019) highlighted the proactive engagement of English language instructors in CPD endeavors, illustrating a comprehensive approach to professional development that includes pedagogical innovation, cultural competence, and reflective teaching practices.

Table 3. *Summary on Attitudes, Views, and Perceptions of College English Language Teachers on Continuing Professional Development*

CPD Practices	Min	Max	Mean	VI
Attitudes	1	4	3.63	Strongly Agree
Views	1	4	3.33	Strongly Agree
Perceptions	1	4	3.51	Strongly Agree
General Mean			3.49	Strongly Agree

Note. $N = 78$; Min = minimum; Max = maximum; VI = verbal interpretation.

Adopted from: Lacs, M. E. B. (2022). Learning activity sheets (LAS) and the English achievement of grade 8 students. *International Multidisciplinary Research Journal*, 4(1), 38-44. E-ISSN: 2378-702X

Legend: 1.00 – 1.75 Very Low Engagement; 1.76 – 2.50 Low Engagement; 2.51 – 3.25 High Engagement; 3.26 – 4.00 Very High Engagement

Table 3 summarizes college English language teachers' attitudes, views, and perceptions towards Continuing Professional Development (CPD). Attitudes towards CPD received a Mean of 3.63, views garnered a Mean of 3.33, and perceptions were rated with a Mean of 3.51, all verbally interpreted as "Strongly Agree." The overall general Mean of 3.49 indicates a robust consensus of positive attitudes towards CPD among the surveyed teachers. This data reflects a strong recognition of CPD's value in their professional lives, highlighting teachers' eagerness to engage in CPD activities for their development and improving student outcomes. However, the slightly lower rating for views suggests areas where CPD program improvements might be needed to fully meet educators' expectations. This presents an opportunity for educational institutions and policymakers to refine CPD offerings based on teacher feedback, ensuring they are aligned with teacher aspirations and classroom realities. Studies by Allen (2019) and Goa (2021) support these findings, emphasizing the significant impact of CPD on enhancing teachers' skills and their strong commitment to ongoing professional

development.

Table 4. *Significant Relationship Between the Extent of Engagement on CPD and CPD Practices of College English Language Teachers in the MIMAROPA Region*

Source of Relationship	Mean	Computed p-value	Computed r-value	Critical r value	Remarks	Decision
Extent of Engagement on CPD	3.28	<.001*	0.86	0.217	Strong Correlation (Relationship is Significant)	Reject Hypothesis
CPD Practices	3.15					

Notes: MIMAROPA = Marinduque, Occidental Mindoro, Oriental Mindoro, Palawan, Romblon, Calapan City and Puerto Princesa City. From: Department of Education, MIMAROPA Region. History. <https://depedmimaroparegion.ph/history/>
 $p < .05$

Table 4 shows a strong positive correlation ($r(76) = .0863$, $p < .001$) between the extent of engagement in Continuing Professional Development (CPD) and CPD practices among college English language teachers in the MIMAROPA region. This significant relationship indicates that teachers who actively participate in CPD are more likely to adopt innovative teaching strategies and stay updated with the latest pedagogical research, which enhances their instructional skills and effectiveness. This suggests that fostering a culture of continuous professional growth leads to more effective teaching methodologies. Teachers are encouraged to view CPD as a valuable tool for improving their practices, while educational institutions should support ample CPD opportunities. These findings align with studies by Faulkner et al. (2019), Mukn et al. (2019), and Bendtsen et al. (2022), which emphasize that active engagement in CPD activities enhances teachers' competence, fosters innovation, and promotes professional growth.

Table 5. *Significant Relationship Between the Extent of Engagement on CPD and Attitudes, Views, And Perceptions of College English Language Teachers in the MIMAROPA Region about CPD Programs*

Source of Relationship	Mean	Computed p-value	Computed r-value	Critical r value	Interpretation	Decision
Extent of Engagement on CPD	3.28	<.001*	0.54	0.217	Moderately Strong Correlation (Relationship is Significant)	Reject Hypothesis
Attitudes, Views, and Perceptions	3.49					

Table 5 shows a moderate positive correlation ($r(76) = .0539$, $p < .001$) between the extent of engagement in Continuing Professional Development (CPD) and the attitudes, views, and perceptions of college English language teachers in the MIMAROPA region towards CPD. This indicates that increased engagement in CPD activities is linked to more favorable attitudes and perceptions, though other factors like the quality and relevance of CPD offerings also play a role. Encouraging higher CPD engagement and improving CPD support systems can enhance teachers' positive perceptions. This aligns with studies by O'Toole (2019) and Nooruddin and Bhamani (2019), which found that greater CPD engagement leads to more positive attitudes and improved teaching outcomes, as teachers find new ways to teach and advance their careers.

Extent of Influence of the CPD Programs and Practices of College English Language Teachers in the MIMAROPA Region to their Performance in ELT and Their Behavior Towards English

The responses from college English language teachers in the MIMAROPA region indicate that Continuing Professional Development (CPD) initiatives significantly enhance their teaching practices and behaviors. Teachers highlighted that CPD programs enable them to address areas for improvement, broaden their teaching skills, and stay current with new knowledge and trends in language education. This proactive approach to professional growth includes rethinking assessment methods, adopting new decision-making approaches, achieving collaborative works, and integrating technology into language instruction. Teachers also noted CPD's role in fostering critical thinking, empowerment, and social responsibility among students, aligning with the principles of the transformative model. The feedback underscores the importance of CPD in enhancing teaching methodologies, promoting innovative practices, and maintaining engagement and relevance in the field. This engagement leads to improved classroom management, enhanced student abilities and behavior, and a commitment to lifelong learning. Institutions should prioritize providing relevant, accessible, and impactful CPD programs to support teachers' professional growth and ultimately improve the quality of English language instruction. Karamatdinova (2023) and Al Balushi (2021) emphasize the necessity of continuous learning for pedagogical effectiveness, with CPD providing current, real-world content that enhances student awareness and engagement. Siregar & Soni Mirizon (2021) and Pramodya Wardani et al. (2023) highlight CPD's role in promoting innovative teaching approaches that prioritize critical thinking and social justice. Mekonnen (2019) observes CPD's impact on improving teaching quality and classroom dynamics, while these studies collectively underline CPD's importance in maintaining relevance and effectiveness in teaching strategies within an evolving educational landscape.

Impacts of Continuing Development Programs to the Pedagogical and Content Knowledge of College English Language Teachers in the MIMAROPA Region

The teachers in the MIMAROPA region report that Continuing Professional Development (CPD) significantly impacts their pedagogical and content knowledge, positively influencing their teaching methods and behaviors. CPD activities enable teachers to tailor course instructions to students' technological inclinations, modify teaching strategies, and integrate real-world applications into lessons, enhancing their relevance and engagement. Teachers highlight that CPD helps them stay updated with current trends, broaden their skills, and implement new teaching methods, such as interactive activities and technology integration, which improve student engagement and learning outcomes. The impact of CPD extends to professional growth, fostering continuous learning, collaboration, and innovative practices that benefit the entire educational ecosystem. Teachers note that CPD empowers them to create dynamic, student-centered learning environments, enhancing critical thinking and social responsibility among students. They also emphasize the role of CPD in refining classroom management and instructional strategies, ensuring high-quality education that meets the evolving needs of students. The findings align with studies by Karamatdinova (2023) and Al Balushi (2021), which emphasize CPD's role in providing contemporary content and fostering continuous learning for pedagogical effectiveness. Spangenberg and Freitas (2019) and Dewi et al. (2020) support the importance of CPD in equipping educators with practical, real-world insights that enhance student engagement. Saricoban and Kirmizi (2020) and Viana and Lu (2021) highlight CPD's contribution to promoting innovative teaching methods and critical engagement. Additionally, Nessaei and Kazemi (2024) and Gess-Newsome et al. (2019) underline the positive correlation between CPD participation and enhanced Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge (TPCK), while Lee et al. (2018) and Barr (2019) emphasize CPD's impact on improving teaching skills and student-teacher interactions. Collectively, these studies underscore CPD's transformative role in advancing educational practices and promoting continuous professional growth among teachers in the MIMAROPA region.

How CPD Programs and Practices of College English Language Teachers in MIMAROPA Region Improve Their Pedagogy

Participating in Continuing Professional Development (CPD) programs has significantly enhanced the pedagogical competence of English language teachers in MIMAROPA, particularly in tertiary education. Teachers have reported improvements in teaching techniques, methods, and curriculum modification to align with the latest trends. CPD initiatives have facilitated technology integration, collaboration, and effective assessment strategies, enabling teachers to create engaging and student-centered lessons. These enhancements have led to better student engagement, critical thinking, and overall learning outcomes. Coaching and mentoring programs have also played a crucial role in building teachers' knowledge, creativity, and critical thinking skills. Action research initiatives have further driven innovation in teaching strategies and curriculum development, fostering a culture of continuous improvement. Participation in communities of practice has provided valuable insights, collaborative opportunities, and professional growth, enhancing teaching methodologies and student engagement. Transformative CPD models have inspired teachers to envision future improvements, adapt to evolving educational needs, and integrate innovative pedagogical approaches, ultimately benefiting student learning experiences. Studies by Nessaei and Kazemi (2024) highlight the positive correlation between CPD engagement and enhanced Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge (TPCK). Spangenberg and Freitas (2019) emphasize the importance of technology integration in teaching, while Barr (2019) and Gess-Newsome et al. (2019) underscore the broad impact of CPD on improving teaching practices and student outcomes. Somantri and Iskandar (2021) discuss the comprehensive nature of CPD in enhancing education and teaching. Additionally, Kang et al. (2018) demonstrate how specific CPD programs can boost teachers' confidence and pedagogical content knowledge. Rachmajanti et al. (2019) and Keh and Swartzendruber (2021) support the significance of coaching and mentoring in professional growth. Research by Bakhshi et al. (2019) and Rahimi et al. (2019) emphasizes the value of action research in promoting innovative teaching strategies. The importance of communities of practice is reflected in the studies by Spangenberg and Freitas (2019) and Lee et al. (2018), highlighting their role in fostering collaboration and continuous professional learning. Finally, the findings of Nessaei and Kazemi (2024) and Barr (2019) support the transformative impact of CPD on teaching practices and student engagement.

Challenges Encountered by English Language Teachers in CPD

The findings reveal that while CPD programs significantly enhance teaching practices, various challenges must be addressed to maximize their effectiveness. Teachers face difficulty applying CPD insights due to resource constraints and heavy workloads, necessitating CPD programs aligned with available resources and consideration of teachers' workloads. Time management, access to high-quality training, and alignment with specific teaching goals are significant challenges, highlighting the need for flexible CPD options. Unfamiliar tasks in CPD programs require adequate support and training, while personal development obstacles like time constraints, financial limitations, and resource access hinder engagement. Institutional barriers, such as a culture prioritizing tenure over knowledge, competitive behaviors, and limited coaching/mentoring programs, impede professional growth. Promoting a sense of community is challenged by workloads, lack of dedicated CPD programs, competitiveness, communication barriers, and geographic dispersion, necessitating a supportive and collaborative environment. Teachers employ strategies such as advocating for more CPD programs, conducting additional research, setting clear goals, effective communication, seeking mentorship, and maintaining flexibility to address action research challenges, aiding in navigating complexities and improving teaching practices. The challenges and strategies identified by teachers align with broader research findings. Kang et al. (2018) highlight the importance of specific CPD programs in

enhancing pedagogical content knowledge. Somantri and Iskandar (2021) emphasize the comprehensive nature of CPD in improving education. Gess-Newsome et al. (2019) discuss the broader impact of CPD on teacher professional knowledge and practice. Nessaei and Kazemi (2024) show a positive correlation between CPD engagement and enhanced Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge (TPCK). Barr (2019) highlights the facilitation of inclusive values and child-centered strategies through CPD programs. Wyatt & Darwish (2022) and Mohammed and Gutema (2023) emphasize the limitations of conventional PD programs and the need for transparent communication and support structures. Kedir and Gutema (2021) and Indrarathne and Dick (2023) discuss the challenges faced by ELT teachers in accessing quality CPD programs and resources. Avillanova & Kuswando (2019) stress the role of collaborative CPD initiatives in bridging theory and practice. Diklitas & Comoglu (2022) highlight the importance of systematic approaches to action research. Fernandez et al. (2022) and Aydin and Ahmet's (2022) emphasize promoting a supportive and inclusive culture within communities of practice. Cruz (2022) and Wong (2023) discuss the motivational aspect of action research in embracing change and innovation. Lastly, the studies by Al-Wadi (2023) and Lee et al. (2018) highlight the role of CPD in promoting continuous professional learning and enhancing pedagogical strategies.

Conclusion

The study concludes that college English language teachers in the MIMAROPA region actively engage in both professional work-based and personal activities for their continuing professional development (CPD), showing very high engagement levels. They participate in publishing articles, seminars, workshops, mentorship programs, self-directed reading, and educational videos. Their CPD practices include high participation in training, awards, coaching and mentoring, communities of practice, and action research, all aimed at enhancing their teaching techniques and methodologies. Teachers hold positive attitudes, views, and perceptions about CPD, believing it improves career chances, teaching skills, and overall effectiveness. There is a strong positive correlation between CPD engagement and CPD practices, indicating that active participation in CPD leads to better teaching practices and professional growth. Additionally, there is a moderately strong positive correlation between CPD engagement and teachers' attitudes, views, and perceptions towards CPD programs. Teachers believe CPD programs improve their performance in English language teaching (ELT) and positively influence their behavior towards English instruction, resulting in enhanced student engagement and learning outcomes. CPD has also been found to improve pedagogical and content knowledge, integrating new teaching strategies, and fostering professional growth. Challenges in CPD include applying insights due to resource constraints, managing heavy workloads, accessing high-quality training, and aligning CPD activities with teaching goals. Teachers address these challenges through further CPD engagements, conducting research, collaboration, flexibility, and reflective practice, emphasizing the need for supportive institutional environments and tailored CPD programs.

Based on the findings and conclusions, the following recommendations are given: Teachers should encourage institutional support for Professional Work-Based Activities and personal endeavors like self-directed reading and watching educational videos to foster a culture of continuous learning. Enhancing CPD practices can be achieved through tailored training programs, offering incentives for certifications, establishing structured coaching and mentoring, creating collaborative communities of practice, promoting action research, and encouraging student-centered development models. Positive attitudes towards CPD can be shaped by conducting awareness campaigns, providing training for effective CPD implementation, and promoting a supportive collaborative learning environment. Further research should explore the relationship between engagement and CPD practices, including surveys or interviews to gauge how engagement levels affect attitudes towards CPD and identifying factors that lead to higher engagement. Assessing CPD's influence on ELT performance and behavior through longitudinal studies, qualitative data, and measuring student outcomes is recommended. Teachers can enhance pedagogical and content knowledge through targeted CPD programs, sharing experiences and best practices, and incorporating feedback mechanisms for continuous improvement. Improving ELT pedagogy involves ongoing training aligned with best practices, promoting mentorship and peer collaboration, encouraging research-based curriculum development, and supporting active participation in professional communities. Addressing CPD participation challenges requires strategies to overcome workload and engagement barriers, providing flexible opportunities, promoting a collaborative community, and encouraging reflective practice and teaching approach refinement through CPD engagements.

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